

An overview of deep learning methods to enhance proteomics data analysis

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Data as the core component

The GIGO concept

Data attributes for training a model

Relevancy: Resemble what you want to predict

Proper classification: Stringently labelled categories

Formatting: Preprocessing to provide standardized input

Accessibility: Local storage of large-scale data

Minimum Data Requirement

The minimums vary with the complexity of the problem, but 100,000 instances in total, across all categories, is a good place to start.

If you have labeled data (i.e. categories A, B, C and D), it's preferable to have an evenly balanced dataset with 25,000 instances of each label; that is, 25,000 instances of A, 25,000 instances of B and so forth.

PDB as enabler of protein structure prediction

One service

One standard file format

Plenty of structures

PDB Statistics: PDB Data Distribution by Processing Software

All Statistics

Data shown include structures solved by any experiment methods.

By Refinement Resolution (Å)

Distribution by structure resolution (Å). Data shown include structures solved by X-ray crystallography or electron microscopy.

Proteomics data and its re-use

Proteomics and machine learning

Machine Learning Deep Learning

Cell Systems

CellPress

Perspective
Artificial intelligence for proteomics and biomarker discovery

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Proteomics and machine learning

Despite of an apparent overload of ML approaches, still many application cases

Challenges:

- Benchmarking -> ProteoBench, MS2AI, DLOmics, Koina
- Synthetic data -> Ethic considerations

Journal of
proteome
research

pubs.acs.org/jpr

Perspective

Toward an Integrated Machine Learning Model of a Proteomics Experiment

Benjamin A. Neely,* Viktoria Dorfer,* Lennart Martens,* Isabell Bludau, Robbin Bouwmeester, Sven Degroeve, Eric W. Deutsch, Siegfried Gessulat, Lukas Käll, Pawel Palczynski, Samuel H. Payne, Tobias Greisager Rehfeldt, Tobias Schmidt, Veit Schwämmle, Julian Uszkoreit, Juan Antonio Vizcaíno, Mathias Wilhelm, and Magnus Palmblad*

Data availability

Current problem:

Each AI method is trained on very specific data sets

For applying deep learning on public data, we need to find, convert, filter, and preprocess to obtain a *balanced* training/validation/testing data set.

MS2AI: automated repurposing of public peptide LC-MS data for machine learning applications FREE

Tobias Greisager Rehfeldt, Konrad Krawczyk, Mathias Bøgebjerg, Veit Schwämmle ✉, Richard Röttger

Bioinformatics, Volume 38, Issue 3, February 2022, Pages 875–877, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btab701>

Variation analysis of MS factors

- 820 projects, 60.500 raw files and 60 TB of data
- Instrument, sample species, gradient length, etc.
- How do these impact ML capabilities?
- How are these handled in the field?

Train -> Validate -> Test

Retention time prediction as use case

How applicable is public data?

Can we blindly use everything and hope that heterogeneity averages out?

No. Too unbalanced experimental setups

PT17

PT19

Limit

Wide

Prediction of peptide fragmentations

Synthetic data as enabler of high-quality predictions from peptide sequence

<http://www.proteometools.org/>

Collision energy

Determines extent of fragmentation events

Given values are not globally applicable

Prosit: proteome-wide prediction of peptide tandem mass spectra by deep learning

Siegfried Gessulat^{1,2,7}, Tobias Schmidt^{1,7}, Daniel Paul Zolg¹, Patroklos Samaras¹, Karsten Schnatbaum³, Johannes Zerweck³, Tobias Knaute³, Julia Rechenberger¹, Bernard Delanghe⁴, Andreas Huhmer⁵, Ulf Reimer³, Hans-Christian Ehrlich², Stephan Aiche², Bernhard Kuster^{1,6*} and Mathias Wilhelm^{1*}

Testing and running the main models is becoming easy

Accessible through a few lines

For tutorials and examples, see
ProteomicsML.org

Koina: Democratizing machine learning for proteomics research

bioRxiv
THE PREPRINT SERVER FOR BIOLOGY

Ludwig Lautenbacher, Kevin L. Yang, Tobias Kockmann, Christian Panse,
 Matthew Chambers, Elias Kahl, Fengchao Yu, Wassim Gabriel, Dulguun Bold, Tobias Schmidt,
 Kai Li, Brendan MacLean, Alexey I. Nesvizhskii, Mathias Wilhelm

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.06.01.596953>

Using predictions to simplify fast-track analysis

Boosting MS1-only Proteomics with Machine Learning Allows 2000 Protein Identifications in Single-Shot Human Proteome Analysis Using 5 min HPLC Gradient

Mark V. Ivanov,* Julia A. Bubis, Vladimir Gorshkov, Daniil A. Abdrakhimov, Frank Kjeldsen, and Mikhail V. Gorshkov

Combine and retrain machine learning models to boost output

Exploiting Charge State Distribution To Probe Intramolecular Interactions in Gas-Phase Phosphopeptides and Enhance Proteomics Analyses

Vladimir Gorshkov* and Frank Kjeldsen

Charge states highly reproducible

Can we extract functional insights for phosphorylations?

No limitations on
sequence
composition

PTMs & cross-linking

Workflow for FDR evaluation in large-scale *E. coli* and *M. pneumoniae* datasets

The input matrix for the amino acids composition path has a dimension of 60 for the peptide sequence by six for the atom counts (C, H, N, O, P and S). Not every peptide is 60 amino acids long, thus 'X'-characters without atomic composition are padded to reach 60 amino acids. This indicates that encoding modified amino acids becomes straightforward, as computing their atomic composition is trivial. Note that for modified amino acids, the atomic composition of the modification is added to the atomic composition of the unmodified residue. This encoding allows the model to learn patterns that generalize to unseen modifications.

Prosit-XL: enhanced cross-linked peptide identification by accurate fragment intensity prediction to study protein-protein interactions and protein structures

Mostafa Kalhor¹, Cemil Can Saylan¹, Mario Picciani¹, Lutz Fischer², Falk Schimweg², Joel Lapin¹, Juri Rappsilber^{2,3,4}, Mathias Wilhelm^{1,5*}

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nature **methods**

ARTICLES

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01301-5>

Check for updates

DeepLC can predict retention times for peptides that carry as-yet unseen modifications

Robbin Bouwmeester^{1,2}, Ralf Gabriels^{1,2}, Niels Hulstaert^{1,2}, Lennart Martens^{1,2,3,4} and Sven Degroeve^{1,2}

What do the models know? Any consistent “rules”?

We can run any number of retention time predictions

Here: peptides simplified to multiples of the same amino acid.

Retention time for different amino acids

Mostly clear patterns

↑ *Retention time vs peptide length* ↑

RT vs. Sequence Length for Each Amino Acid, DeepLC prediction

DeepLC model

RT vs. Sequence Length for Each Amino Acid, Prosit prediction

Prosit model

Workflow

Background tryptic peptide sequence:

AAAAAAAK

Target amino acid which moves from N to C
 terminus

XAAAAAAK

AXAAAAAK

AAXAAAAK

AAAXAAAK

AAAAXAAK

AAAAAXAK

AAAAAAXK

Insert Input

Predict fragmentation ions
 {Predict_model}

Create ion list
 {Create_ion_list}

Normalize Predictions
 {normalize_ions}

Subtracted background

Visualization

Statistical tests

LAAAAAAK

ALAAAAAAK

AALAAAAK

AAALAAAK

AAAAALAK

AAAAAALK

Dashed lines: background

-- Ala b lon (+1) Background - - - Ala y lon (+1) Background — b lons (+1) - - - y lons (+1)
 — Ala b lon (+2) Background - - - Ala y lon (+2) Background — b lons (+2) - - - y lons (+2)

Picking out the main trends

Ion Intensity Heatmap (% Change): Arginine 's Positional Impact for Prosit

Prosit	b_3^+	b_3^{++}	b_4^{++}	b_6^+
P – Value	0.016	0.020	0.034	0.031
Correlation	0.833	0.334	0.626	-0.890

How to use the predictions: MS rescoring as main application

MCP PERSPECTIVE

FDR for peptide identification enhanced by matching with predicted retention times and spectra

Rescoring Peptide Spectrum Matches: Boosting Proteomics Performance by Integrating Peptide Property Predictors Into Peptide Identification

Authors

Mostafa Kalthor, Joel Lapin, Mario Picciani, and Mathias Wilhelm

Rescoring is widely used in spectrum to spectrum matching

Also used for direct spectrum matching such as for data-independent acquisition (e.g. with DIA-NN)

-> FDR control very difficult (no easy generation of target matches)

nature methods

Article

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-025-02719-x>

Assessment of false discovery rate control in tandem mass spectrometry analysis using entrapment

Received: 3 June 2024

Bo Wen¹, Jack Freestone², Michael Riffle¹, Michael J. MacCoss¹, William S. Noble^{1,3} & Uri Keich²

Accepted: 24 April 2025

Predict the right direction: de novo sequencing

How to represent a fragmentation spectrum?

CNN -> Transformer -> PointNet

Is there enough information in the spectra?

Should refinement within species provide better results?

Why do tryptic peptides get better performance even when the model was trained on non-tryptic peptides?

Nice review:

Deep learning methods for de novo peptide sequencing

27 May 2024, Version 1

Review

ChemRxiv[®]

Wout Bittremieux , William Stafford Noble

Show author details

Tryptic vs. non-tryptic

A

B

Architecture of CasaNovo

Conclusions

Deep learning in proteomics can be challenging due to data heterogeneity

Major focus is on retention time and fragmentation

But there are many other applications

De novo sequencing could bring a quantum leap, but will it? Consider enzyme and species bias?

Can we use these models to generate actual knowledge? Did they learn new sufficiently simple patterns we do now know?